

Universität Potsdam

Information on Data Protection for the PROTEST-AIRT project

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship (Grant Agreement 101057156)

We process your personal data in compliance with the applicable data protection regulations, in particular the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Brandenburg Data Protection Act (BbgDSG).

The data controller is:

University of Potsdam
Represented by the president, Prof. Oliver Günther, Ph.D.
Am Neuen Palais 10
14469 Potsdam
Phone: +49 331 977-0
Telefax: +49 331-97 21 63
www.uni-potsdam.de

Purpose of the processing

Your data will be processed as part of a research project that explores the emerging dissent against the global air transport industry. This study includes various data sources such as media texts (newspapers or online reports), interviews, visual materials such as photographs and other innovative techniques. Written notes (including verbatim quotations) will be taken and potentially published in **an anonymized form**. The PROTEST-AIRT project is expected to advance the global and European political debate on both the future of air transport and the diverse impacts of the industry (particularly in the context of the climate emergency).

Lawfulness of processing

The legal basis for data processing is your consent to the processing of personal data (Art. 6 para. 1 sentence 1 lit. a GDPR). Insofar as political opinions are expressed in the context of the planned interviews, the legal basis for data processing is additionally derived from Art. 9 para. 2 lit. a GDPR (consent to the processing of special categories of personal data).

Withdrawal of consent

You have the right to withdraw your consent at any time and without reason. The withdrawal of consent does not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal.

Duration of data processing

Any written notes produced during this informal conversation will be digitalized and later stored in an external hard drive while being processed, and this external hard drive will be encrypted and kept at a secure location at the University of Potsdam. The physical notes in paper will be destroyed after the pseudonymized digital file has been created. Contact information will be kept only in the consent form for notetaking, and it will only be used if the researcher decides to formally include you in a later phase of the project (for example, in an in-depth interview). Your name will be linked to pseudonymized digital

file through a code. Any code linking your name to your pseudonymized digital file will be destroyed at the end of the project (June 30th, 2024). At that point your data will be completely anonymized.

Recipients of your data

Any notes produced during this conversation could be used in an anonymized form in scientific publications in journals, conferences, public lectures and in communication activities designed for non-academic publics, for example, as part of public education apropos the air transport industry only to provide additional context. Any excerpts will include a footnote indicating the day and place in which the informal conversation took place.

Your rights:

You have the right to obtain from the controller confirmation as to whether or not your personal data is being processed, and, if that is the case, access to the personal data and additional information (right of access). You also have the right to obtain from the controller without undue delay the rectification of inaccurate personal data. If the legal requirements of Art. 17 or 18 GDPR are met, you are entitled to the erasure of your personal data or to a restriction of processing. Please note that restricted processing of the data may not be possible in every instance. You have the right to receive your personal data in a structured, standard, and machine-readable format or to request the transfer to another controller (right to data portability, Art. 20 GDPR). Furthermore, you may object to the processing of your personal data under the conditions set forth in Art. 21 GDPR.

In order to exercise your rights, we kindly request that you contact:

Dr. Alexander Araya López
August-Bebel-Straße 89
14482 Potsdam
Haus 7, Raum 3.30
Phone: [ADD PHONE NUMBER]
E-Mail: [ADD EMAIL]

Access to your personal data can be requested from the Chief Information Officer (University of Potsdam, Karl-Liebknecht-Str. 24-25, 14476 Potsdam). The corresponding form can be found on his website: <https://www.uni-potsdam.de/de/praesidialbereich/praesident-vizepraesidenten/cio.html>.

You can contact the university's Data Protection Officer if you have questions regarding data protection:

[ADD FULL NAME]
Am Neuen Palais 10
14469 Potsdam
Phone: [ADD PHONE NUMBER]
Telefax: [ADD FAX NUMBER]
E-Mail: [ADD EMAIL]

If you think that the processing of your personal data infringes the GDPR, then you have the right to lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority for data protection.